

EPRVIII Instruments

Instrument	EPRVIII Presenter	Date of expected first light	Date of expected full capabilities	Wavelength range (nm)	Expected best precision	Telescope name	Telescope location	Telescope aperture	Availability	Instrument paper citation(s)	Very short description
SALT/HRS	Lisa Crause	9/2013	early 2018	370-890	TBD! Hopefully <3 m/s	SALT	Sutherland, South Africa	~10m	SALT partnership	Crause+ 2014 SPIE 9147E 6T	Stabilised dual-channel (370-890 nm), fibre-fed vacuum echelle, R~70k high stability (HS) mode for PRV (double scrambler + iodine cell or simultaneous Th-Ar). Pipeline for HS under development, but instrument designed to reach <5 m/s.
MINERVA	Nate McCrady	12/2015	11/2016	480-690	~0.9 m/s	MINERVA	Mt Hopkins, AZ, USA	4x0.7m	PI-only	Swift+ 2015 JATIS 1(2) 027002	Octagonal fiber-fed, robotic, temperature and pressure stabilized, iodine cell, R=75,000 echelle spectrometer.
Veloce	Chris Tinney	3/2018 for "Rosso" (580-950 nm)	2020	380-950	<0.3 m/s internal sub-1m/s on sky goal	AAT	Coonabarabran NSW, Australia	4m	Facility	under preparation	IFU fibre-fed temperature and pressure controlled, red wavelength R=80,000 spectrograph. Simultaneous single-mode lasercomb and ThXe calibration. Eventually to be 350-0950nm with addition of Verde and Azzurro cameras
PFS2	Johanna Teske	2/2018	mid 2018	380-690	~0.5 m/s on sky	Magellan II	Las Campanas, Chile	6.5m	PI-only	Crane+ 2006 SPIE 6269E 31 Crane+ 2008 SPIE 7014E 79 Crane+ 2010 SPIE 7735E 53 (hopefully 2018 with upgrades!)	Optical, stabilized RV spectrograph on Magellan II. I2 cal. Upgrade = octagonal fiber feed, pupil slicer, new detector with smaller pixels, R~120,000.
PARAS-2	Abhijit Chakraborty	12/2019	mid 2020	380-690	0.5 m/s on sky	2.5m Telescope	Mt. Abu, India	2.5m	PI-only	under preparation	Fiber-fed, stabilized RV spectrograph (R~100000) under stabilized environment (T~0.001K at 24C; Vacuum Pressure at 0.0001mbar), double srambler, octagonal-circular fiber combination; simultaneous ThAr calibration.
HARPS3	Samantha Thompson	end-2019	early 2020	380-690	< 0.5 m/s	Isaac Newton (INT)	Roque de los Muchachos, Canary Islands, Spain	2.5m	Facility	Thompson+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 6F	Stabilised, fibre-fed, R=115,000, 380-690nm, robotic operation, full Stokes dual-beam polarimeter in Cass adapter
TOU	Bo Ma	11/2016	10/2017	380-900	~0.8 m/s on sky	UF 50-inch	Mt. Hopkins, AZ, USA	1.27 m	PI-only	Ge+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 6I	Optical, 380-900nm, R~100,000, ThAr calibration. Instrument stability ~1m/s.
iSHELL	Bryson Cale	10/2016	10/16	1100-5300	TBD, < 5m/s	IRTF	Maunakea, HI, USA	3m	Facility	Rayner+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 84 Rayner+ 2012 SPIE 8446E 2C	R-70,000, ¹³ CH ₄ cell for calibration, Cassegrain mounted
MINERVA-R	Cullen Blake	1/2018	3/2018	820-920	<1 m/s instrumental	MINERVA	Mt. Hopkins, AZ, USA	0.7m	PI-only	Sliski+2017 - submitted	R~50,000, SM fiber, UNe and etalon calibration, 0.7 meter telescope
MAROON-X	Andreas Seifahrt	1/2019	05/2019	500-900	<0.3 m/s internal <1 m/s on-sky	Gemini North	Maunakea, HI, USA	8.2m	public	Seifahrt+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 18	R~80,000, fiber-fed, stabilized RV spectrograph with pupil slicer and doubler scrambler. Rb-traced etalon calibrator. Optimized for M-dwarfs
iLocator	Jonathan Crass	Fall 2019	12/2019	971-1270	<0.4 m/s internal <0.7 m/s on-sky	Large Binocular Telescope	Mount Graham, AZ, USA	2x8.2m	PI-only	Crepp+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 19	Single-mode fiber fed stabilized NIR spectrograph (YJ band). Rb-locked etalon calibration system.
PARVI	Gautam Vasisht	Fall 2018	Fall 2019	1250-1800	1.0 m/s (req) 0.3 m/s (goal)	Hale Telescope	Mt. Palomar, CA, USA	5.1m	Facility	None	Single-mode fiber fed stabilized NIR spectrograph (JH band). EOM comb based calibration system. R~100,000.
NIRPS	Rene Doyon	2019	2019	970-1810	~< 1 m/s	La Silla 3.6-m	La Silla, Chile	3.6m	ESO/public	None	Stabilized YJH R=100000 fiber-fed near-IR spectrograph, AO (0.4") and high-efficiency fiber (0.9")
SPIROU	Claire Moutou	3/2018	8/2018	980-2350	1 m/s	CFHT	Maunakea, HI, USA	3.6m	Facility	Donati+2017 exoplanet handbook	FP-stabilized YJHK fiber-fed spectropolarimeter. R=70k. Cryogenic at 80K.
HPF	Sam Halverson	9/2017	11/2017	810-1290	~1 m/s	Hobby-Eberly Telescope	McDonald Observatory, Texas, USA	~10m	Facility	Mahadevan+ 2014 SPIE 9147E 1G	Stabilized z/Y/J-band NIR spectrometer with EOM frequency comb, monolithic double scrambler
IRD	Masashi Omiya	8/9/2017	10/2017	970-1750	1 m/s	Subaru	Maunakea, HI, USA	8.2m	Facility	Kotani+ 2014 SPIE 9147E 14	Fiber-fed stabilized NIR (Y,J,H) spectrograph for the Subaru, laser frequency comb, ultra-low thermal expansion ceramic optical components
CARMENES	Ansgar Reiners	10/2015	01/2016	520-1710	1 m/s	Calar Alto 3.5m	Calar Alto, Spain	3.5m	Facility	Quirrenbach+ 2014 SPIE 9147E 1F	Two stabilized R~90,000 spectrographs (520-980nm, 980-1710nm), simultaneous calibration
GIARPS	Monica Rainer	03/2017	mid 2018	340-2450	1 m/s (visible) 3 m/s (infrared)	TNG	Roque de los Muchachos, Canary Islands, Spain	3.6m	Public	Claudi+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 3H	Simultaneous observations with HARPS-N (visible, 340-690nm, R=115,000) and GIANO-B (infrared, 950-2450 nm, R=50,000)
NEID	Paul Robertson / Chris Schwab	1/2019	mid 2019	380-1000	~0.3 m/s initial w/ path to 0.1 m/s	3.5m WIYN	Kitt Peak, AZ, USA	3.5m	Public	Halverson+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 6P Schwab+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 7H	Ultra-precise broadband optical spectrometer. Public accessibility, optimized for both bright and faint (read: TESS) targets.
EXPRES	Ryan Blackman	5/2017 (front end, vacuum enclosure), 11/2017 (science)	12/2017	380-900	<0.3 m/s	Discovery Channel Telescope	Happy Jack, AZ, USA	4.3m	PI+Lowell Consortium	Jurgenson+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 6T	Fiber-fed, stabilized RV spectrograph, R=150,000, Menlo LFC, double scrambler/pupil slicer, chromatic exposure meter
ESPRESSO	Francesco Pepe	11/2017	1/10/2018	380-780	0.1m/s	VLT	Cerro Paranal, Chile	(4x)8m	ESO/public	Pepe+ 2013 The Messenger 153, 6	Stabilized, cross-disperser, fiber-fed echelle spectrograph with high spectral resolution for ultra-high RV precision and high-fidelity spectroscopy. Can work with either one or 4 UTs of the VLT.
KPF	Arpita Roy	1/2020	mid 2020	440-850	0.3m/s (goal) 0.5m/s (req)	Keck I	Maunakea, HI, USA	10m	Facility, public	Gibson+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 70	Stabilized, fiber-fed, all-Zerodur, optical spectrometer (R>85,000) providing access to faint targets, especially transiting systems, on 10m Keck aperture
GCLEF	Sagi Ben-Ami	2022	2023	350-950	0.1m/s	GMT	Las Campanas, Chile	25.4m	Facility	Szentgyorgyi+ 2016 SPIE 9908E 22	Stabilized, fiber-fed, composite bench, visible, multimode (R=20K, 40K and 100K), First Light GMT instrument